

NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL
SCIENTIFIC SERVICES

OPERATIONS REPORT
OF A DEMONSTRATION THEMATIC MULTISPECTRAL
SCANNER SURVEY
OF 24 SELECTED AREAS OF
THE UNITED KINGDOM
IN 1983

Hunting Geology and Geophysics Limited
Elstree Way,
Borehamwood,
Hertfordshire WD6 1SB

Telephone: 01-953 6161
Telex: 23517 HUNBOR G
Cable: ASTEREO BOREHAMWOOD

Project: 280 246
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SUMMARY

The Natural Environment Research Council, Scientific Service Division on 25th May 1983 commissioned by telex a second season of flying and acquisition of data of 24 selected areas of the United Kingdom where ground research projects by University and N.E.R.C. units were being conducted.

The contract period, from availability of equipment, was limited to a 25 day period in 1983, whereupon acquisition would cease, flown or not.

The aircraft used for this second season was a Navajo Chieftain owned and operated by N.E.R.C. from Kidlington through their handling agents, CSE Aviation Limited.

The following sectionalised report describes the field operation and equipment in detail together with an area by area detail summary.

PART I

OPERATIONS REPORT

1. INTRODUCTION

The Thematic Scanner Survey described in this report was carried out by Hunting Geology and Geophysics Limited on behalf of the Scientific Services Division of Natural Environment Research Council (N.E.R.C.) of Swindon, Wiltshire. The areas surveyed totalled 24 as detailed in Purchase Order F3/G6/229 of 23rd June 1983 and outlined in Text Figures 1 and 2 for 1983. The 1984 flying also covered by this contractual document will be the subject of a further report on completion of that season's flying.

A Piper Navajo/Chieftain aircraft supplied by NERC and crewed by CSE Aviation Limited, fitted with a survey camera and a Daedalus AADS1268 Thematic Scanner commenced flying on 15th August 1983 and was terminated temporarily on 20th September 1983, with a further period after the break from 1st to 5th October 1983.

The following report describes in detail the acquisition aspects of this second season of AADS1268 surveying in the United Kingdom.

2. INVOLVED PERSONNEL

N.E.R.C. Co-ordinator and Contractual Representative:-

Dr. David Williams
laterly Mr. John Plevin

CSE Aviation Limited:-

Captain/Pilots - H. John
J. Gledhill
A. Gunter Smith

Aircraft Engineers - from CSE pool

Hunting Geology and Geophysics Limited:-

Field Project Leader/
Survey Photo Navigator - J. Cook

AADS1268 Engineer/
Operators - D. Nind
R. Westland

Operations Manager - R.D. Williams

3. FLYING OPERATIONS

3.1 Aircraft and Operational Bases

The Survey was flown throughout using the N.E.R.C. Chieftain aircraft, registration GBBXX, based mainly at Kidlington (Oxford) Airport, with landings at Edinburgh, Teeside, Connington and East Midlands, Cardiff and Stornaway Airports, when flying large detailed areas or long transits were involved.

3.2 Flying Specification and Weather Tolerances

In general the areas to be flown were scattered throughout the United Kingdom and, with the exception of areas in Scotland, were flown from the aircraft's base at Kidlington. This base gave the flying crews the best possible servicing facilities and the best photographic dark rooms for quick look processing.

The specifications for height, haze, cloud and flight direction were laid down by N.E.R.C. prior to commencement of the flying programme. These were continually subject to alteration by the client in the light of prevailing weather conditions, and availability of field research crews relative to the maximum contractual availability of the scanner equipment, namely 25 days. The finally achieved flying acquisition details are as follows:-

AREA NO.	NAME	HEIGHT M/FT	DIRECTION	GROUND SPEED KMS	NO. OF RUNS
2	Gedney Hill	6,600 ft	020 Degrees	160	18
11	Swansea Bay	1,500 ft	E/W	105	2
12	Coed-y-Brenin	3,000 m	N	170	3
13	Portsmouth	5,000 ft	N	170	3
14	Loch Leigh	4,500 ft	N	170	4
16	Derbyshire	2,400 ft	W	150	8
		2,500 ft	E/W	155	8
18	Loch Assynt	7,500 ft	N/S	170	9
19A	Dartford	7,000 ft	N/S	170	4
19B	Henley	7,000 ft	N/S	170	4
19C	Poole	2,000 m	N	170	4

AREA NO.	NAME	HEIGHT M/FT	DIRECTION	GROUND SPEED KMS	NO. OF RUNS
22	N. Yorkshire	5,500 ft	N	170	3
		2,200 ft		140	10
27	Snowdon	3,500 m	N	170	3
34	Nottingham	variable	N	170	7
36	Winchester/	800	N	170	1
	Petersfield	1,600 m	N	110	3
43	Chatteris	6,600 m	N/S	170	18
46	Solent	6,600 ft	E/NW/NE	170	4
47	Norwich	3,000 m	E/W/S/N	135	8
	Strumpshaw	2,000 m			
	Marsh	1,000 m			
Reserve Areas					
	Loch Leven	4,100 ft	NW	150	2
	Thetford	2,000 m	E	135	3
	Anglesey	800 m	NE	140	1
	Theobalds Park	5,000 ft	E/W	170	3
	Horseley Mere	2,000 m	N	140	5
	Weston-super-Mare	2,000 m	N	170	3
	Swindon area Tests	1,500 ft	variable	105	9

3.3 Navigation

Other than the standard aircraft navigation aids, no specific navigation equipment was added to the N.E.R.C. survey aircraft. However a survey navigator and a wide angle survey camera were supplied and installed, the camera being used on specific scanner lines. Standard forward overlap was maintained throughout the survey period.

3.4 Survey Diary. Progress and Serviceability

The following is a summary of events

August 1983

9th Installation of equipment in aircraft commenced at Kidlington (Oxford) Airport.

10th/13th Installation, inspections and tests continued at Kidlington (Oxford) Airport, office, and dark room set up at airport.

14th First 1983 season ATM flight, 8 runs over and around NERC Swindon.

15th 2 sorties over Gedney Hill area, 18 runs in total flown.

16th Weather prevented survey.

17th Sortie 7 over Portsmouth attempted. 3 runs flown under continuous cloud build up. Data and sortie aborted.

18th Sortie 8 flown over 3 areas in North Wales, Barmouth, Snowdon, Anglesey, 7 runs achieved. Landed RAF valley refuelled then flew sortie 9 East Midlands, 5 runs flown at varying heights, 1 later aborted due cloud.

19th Sorties 10 and 11 flown, 3 runs over Thetford, 8 runs over Strumpshaw Marsh at varying heights, 5 runs over Horsey Mere.

20th No flying, targets exhausted.

21st No flying. Stand down.

22nd Transit to Scotland. Weather problem.

23rd/24th No flying, poor weather conditions, ATC permits.

25th Sortie 12 Loch Leven 2 runs achieved.

26th No flying, pilot change over/weather.

27th A Hunting day.

28th Sortie 15 flown over Leith, 4 runs achieved.

30th Aircraft equipment malfunction no productive flight.

31st Weather prevented survey.

September

1st to 4th Weather prevented survey.

5th Sorties 20 and 21 flown, over Winchester 1 run, Dorchester 4 runs, Weston-super-Mare 3 runs, Swindon 2 runs, (1 only used) Henley 4 runs, Dartford 4 runs, Theobalds Park 3 runs. The central London run LAP to Thames Barrage was flown on sortie 21 but not required by N.E.R.C.

6th Sortie 22 flown over Solent, 4 runs achieved. After a refuelling stop sortie 23 flown over Derbyshire, (Bakewell) 8 runs being achieved. A further refuelling stop made and sortie 24 flown over Portsmouth, 3 reflights achieved.

7th Sorties 25/26 flown over North Yorkshire. 14 runs achieved, 2 flying heights used.

8th to 12th Weather prevented survey.

13th Sortie 29 achieved, 18 runs across the Chatteris area.

14th Sortie 32 flown. Nottingham University area. 7 runs at various heights ranging from 1650 to 13200 feet.

15th Weather prevented survey.

16th Aircraft utilised by N.E.R.C.

17th to 19th Weather prevented survey

20th to 30th Aircraft utilised by N.E.R.C. Equip. reinstalled am 30th.

October 1st Weather prevented survey

2nd Sortie 34 flown over Buxton area 16 and Humber Estuary. 8 runs being flown over Buxton and 4 in Humber Estuary.
* The latter data has since been left in Obeyance.

3rd Weather prevented survey.

4th Sortie 37 flown from Cardiff. 2 runs over Swansea Bay flown before weather aborted sortie.

5th Sortie 39 covering Winchester area flown. 3 runs achieved, aircraft returned to passenger configuration pm.

November

11th Sortie 41 flown over Loch Assynt, 9 runs achieved, 5 only processed.

This completed the NERC flying programme for 1983, the last area having been attempted and achieved during a Hunting agreed mission. During the entire period reviewed above the survey camera was fully serviceable. With the exception of two short periods namely 25th August Loch Leven, 6th September Portsmouth when minor faults in channels 8 and 9 and channel 1 respectively were noted, the scanner was fully serviceable. In the above noted periods, lines possibly affected were reflight. All other reflight's were related to offline navigation or cloud incursion affecting the imagery.

4. EQUIPMENT

4.1 Survey Camera

The camera used on this years NERC flying was a wild RC8 wide angle survey camera. This unit was manually operated throughout the survey period by the survey navigator who adjusted the forward overlap to suit the area being surveyed. The camera was installed in the forward camera hole of the NERC aircraft and produced throughout 9 x 9 format black/white images, the unit had a 6" focal length and was fitted with a 15 Uag 396 lens. The processing of all exposed film was carried out in the photo laboratories of Hunting Surveys Ltd Borehamwood who produced a total of 1553 prints over specified areas. The scale of these prints vary with the differing heights of each area. Photo cover was not commissioned over all areas.

4.2 Airborne Thematic Mapper

The equipment chosen for the 1983 NERC contract was again the Daedalus Enterprises Inc AADS 1268 ATM 11 Channel Scanner.

This complete sensor unit comprises a scan head, spectrometer and digitiser coupled in, on this survey, to a AADS 1840 HDDT to B/W film conversion unit, a HDDT playback unit and a Samgamo Sabre III tape recorder, Model 3630 1" machine. This combination of units enabled on site production of HDDTs and Quick Look 5" wide negative film of any one selected channel at Kidlington. Scan speeds of 12.5, 25 and 50 scans/second were selected for the areas flown and the S bend correction was applied to all areas flown.

Infrared Reference Source

2 controllable thermal blackbodies with a temperature range of - 15°C to +50°C with respect to scan head heat sink temperature.

Figure 9 outlines the functional operations of both the scanner head and the spectrometer.

TABLE 4

<u>Primary Channel #</u>	<u>Spectral band in #</u>
1	0.42 - 0.45
2	0.45 - 0.52
3	0.52 - 0.60
4	0.605 - 0.625
5	0.63 - 0.69
6	0.695 - 0.75
7	0.76 - 0.90
8	0.91 - 1.05
9	1.55 - 1.75
10	2.08 - 2.35
11	8.5 - 14.0

4.3 Radio Communication Units

4 SMC 317L6 3 watt, 6 channel 2 way units were supplied to assist in air/ground movements during proposed area survey period. The radios were again tuned to the licenced frequency of 169.275 Mhz. This licence having previously been allocated to the Hunting Group by the Home Office.

5. DATA ACQUIRED AND PRESENTED

5.1 Onsite

9 High Density Data Tapes (HDDTS) and one channel of B/W prints of quicklook imagery were produced progressively throughout the survey period. The HDDTS were carried forward sortie to sortie until a total capacity had been achieved.

FIGURE 9

9 x 9 photo cover was taken on all lines flown except offshore flights where no landfall was visible. In total (including additional prints of the Horsey Mere Area) 1553 B/W prints were produced.

5.2 Final Presentations

(a) The field produced HDDTs were converted to CCTs in two stages. Stage one being carried out at Dundee University under the supervision of Dr. Peter Bayliss. This work comprised the initial conversion stage to CCT in a channel by channel stage as flown and without correction. Stage two of this conversion was carried out in the Hunting laboratories at Elstree on their HP 3000 computer where all channels of data per line flown were recompiled with start and end scans correlated. No flight line was split onto a second tape. Supplementary to this standard presentation, lines 1357911 of the Loch Assynt area were presented in a requested unblocked format.

(b) All photo cover taken throughout the ATM flying has been presented as 9" x 9" black and white prints with their respective negatives. An index plot of the lines flown, showing prints and run numbers, at a scale of 1:50,000 has also been presented.

(c) A report of operations in 5 copies.

5.3 CCT Format

Tape 0.5 ins x 2400 feet

Format: Huntings 1 band sequential format.

Density: 1600 b.p.i tracks 9

Byte size: 8 bits.

Channels: 11 per line flown, recorded in the following manner.

The tape is written on a 9 track, 1600 b.p.i. no parity CCT contained on a standard 10.5" reel. The basic word size for the header and ancillary data is 2 bytes and is organised as follows:

The tape will contain files each of which hold the data for one channel of a complete flight line.

Each file will begin with 4 header records of 50 bytes. These are followed by records 7500 bytes long which hold the data for 10 consecutive scan lines.

The last record on tape will be back filled with nulls if it is not full.

Each scan line is 750 bytes long. The first 23 bytes and the last 11 bytes of each scan line contain calibration or housekeeping data. The video data is contained in the remaining 716 bytes. (see table 5 for layout).

A tape will contain a maximum of 48,000 scan lines.

The number of files on the tape is given by the formula:

$$n = \frac{48000}{spf}$$

where n is number of files on the tape which is the nearest whole number below.

spf is the number of scan lines in a complete flight line.

48000 is the total number of scan lines allowed on one tape.

TABLE 5

SCAN LINE FORMAT

BYTE	INFORMATION
1, 2, 3, 4	START OF FRAME CODE
	01010110 10100101 10100110 10101111

5	RUN NUMBER/EXTEND LINE CODE
6, 7, 8	LINE COUNT (BCD)
9, 10, 11, 12	THUMBWHEEL SWITCH SETTINGS (BCD)
13, 14	CALIBRATION SOURCE 1 (BCD)
15, 16	CALIBRATION SOURCE 2 (BCD)
17, 18, 19, 20, 21	EXTERNAL DIGITAL DATA EXCEPT THAT FIRST 2 MSB OF WORD 17 TO BE SCAN SPEED.
	00 = 12.5 SCANS/SEC
	01 = 25 SCANS/SEC
	10 = 50 SCANS/SEC
22	CHANNEL NUMBER (4 LSB)
23	DIGITIZED BB1
24 to 739	DIGITIZED VIDEO DATA
740	DIGITIZED BB2
741 to 750	END OF FRAME CODE (10101010.....)

TABLE 6

HEADER STRUCTURE

<u>BYTE #</u>	<u>DESCRIPTION</u>
1-32	EBCDIC - DAEDALUS ENTERPRISES AADS1268
33-53	EBCDIC - (FLIGHT ALTITUDE)
54-60	EBCDIC - (ESTIMATED GROUND SPEED)
61	(DATE - DAY)
62	(DATE - MONTH)
63	(DATE - YEAR)
64-80	NOT APPLICABLE
81	ACTIVE CHANNELS 1 THROUGH 8 (1=ACTIVE) - CH #1=MSB
82	ACTIVE CHANNELS 9 THROUGH 16 (1=ACTIVE) - CH #9=MSB
83	NOT APPLICABLE
90	11 (NUMBER OF CHANNELS ON THIS TAPE)
91	8 (NUMBER OF BITS IN PIXEL)
92-93	20 (BYTE LOCATION OF START OF VIDEO WITHIN SCAN DATA)

94-95	1 (BYTE LOCATION OF 1st CALIBRATION AREA)
96-97	716 (NUMBER OF PIXELS IN SCAN)
98-99	19 (NUMBER OF CAL. ELEMENTS IN 1st CALIBRATION AREA)
100-101	2340 (RECORD SIZE IN BYTES)
102	3 (NUMBER OF CHANNELS PER RECORD)
103	NOT APPLICABLE
104	3 (NUMBER OF RECORDS PER DATA SET)
105-106	70 (LENGTH OF ANCILLARY DATA IN BYTES)
107	1 (LINE INTERLEAVED)
108-109	20 (1st PIXEL #)
110-111	735 (LAST PIXEL #)
112-1778	NOT APPLICABLE
1779-1780	736 (BYTE LOCATION OF 2nd CALIBRATION AREA)
1781-1782	1 (NUMBER OF ELEMENTS IN 2nd CALIBRATION AREA)
1783-1784	NOT APPLICABLE
1785-1786	3 (NUMBER OF CHANNELS IN 1st RECORD OF DATA SET)
1787-1788	736 (NUMBER OF ELEMENTS PER SCAN PER CHANNEL)
1789-1796	NOT APPLICABLE
1797-2940	FILL ZEROS
2941-3000	EBCDIC (SITE #, SITE NAME, LINE #, FLIGHT DIR., FLIGHT TIME)
3001-3060	FILL ZEROS

NOTE: All information is binary-right justified in field except Bytes 1-60 and 2940-3000 which contain EBCDIC coded information.

6. MATERIALS SUPPLIED TO CLIENT

6.1 Survey Film

A total of 1553 9" x 9" black/white survey photographs and their associated negatives covering all areas flown bar Swansea Bay, The Solent and Theobalds Park have been supplied. This figure includes duplicate prints of the Horsey Mere Area, ordered as a supplementary to the original contract.

6.2 Quicklook Imagery

Uncorrected B/W prints of one channel in 5" wide strips along all lines flown (including the Humber Estuary) were produced from the field equipment and presented to client for inspection.

6.3 CCTs

A total of 134 master CCTs covering all areas flown except, Area 18 Loch Assynt lines 2, 4, 6, 8; Area 16 Bakewell Derbyshire lines 1 to 8 inclusive flown west; Area 22 North Yorkshire lines 1, 2, 6 to 10 low level and the Humber Estuary were presented progressively to the client.

6.4 HDDTs

The field produced HDDTs covering all areas flown are held by Huntings pending a directive as to their disposal within the next 12 months.

6.5 Flight Maps

A full set of 1:50,000 scale ordnance survey map sheets with recovered flight line plots superimposed of each area flown have been supplied with the photo prints.

6.6 Operations Report

Finally, an outline operations report in 5 copies has been presented.

PART II
DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

TABLE 1

General Contractual Flying Specification

Weather Restrictions to Flying Programme

1. Cloud - Sites can be flown in cloud free or under a complete cloud cover. For cloud free up to 5% patchy cloud or shadow can be allowed.

For patchy cloud the site should not be flown without clearance from the NERC project co-ordinator.

Sites should not be flown without clearance where the overall luminescence is constantly varying.
2. Precipitation - No restriction due to recent rain is necessary.
3. Wind- Whilst calm conditions are preferable the limiting factor is likely to be turbulence effects on the aircraft.
4. Haze/Visibility - In hazy conditions the scanner operator/crew will be responsible for advising on the likely effect and which channels will be affected. The NERC co-ordinator will then decide. In low light conditions the scanner operator must decide if he can record a satisfactory signal by adjusting the gain.
5. Time - Ideally all flying between 9.30 and 16.00 hours. However if we get clear mornings and/or clear evenings the NERC co-ordinator in conjunction with the crew may alter this.

General

If the aircraft flies and the weather closes in the principal of flying a target and see should be adopted rather than returning empty handed.

Photography - 30% forward overlap unless stated otherwise-

Radios

- (i) Can the crew transmit on the aircraft radio so that field teams can listen? They should transmit whilst on target and at the end.
- (ii) The two way radios should be used as needed.
- (iii) Radio silence should be observed with the scanner on and the transponder should be off. These effect the data recording.

Area Covered

The scanner should be switched on for the minimum amount of recording to save data processing.

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

NERC 1983 SURVEY

Area No. and Name	2 GEDNEY HILL	Map Sheet Nos.
Flying Height (metres)	2030	Direction Flown 020°
Flight Conditions	MEDIUM HAZE	No. of Lines 18
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	87	No. of Scan Lines 140,600
Film Forward Overlap (%)	60	No. of CCTs 19
Ground Speed (knots)	160	Scan Speed rps 25
Time Flown (GMT)	1225-1359: 1610-1736	Tape Footage 1587
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Area No. and Name	11 SWANSEA BAY	Map Sheet Nos.
Flying Height (metres)	462	Direction Flown E/W
Flight Conditions	CLOUD AT 1500 FEET POOR VISIBILITY	No. of Lines 2
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	0	No. of Scan Lines 51,400
Film Forward Overlap (%)	N/A	No. of CCTs 7
Ground Speed (Knots)	105	Scan Speed rps 50
Time Flown (GMT)	1050 - 1107 ABANDONED DUE RAIN/VIS/LIGHT CONDITIONS	Tape Footage 1261
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

NERC 1983 SURVEY

Area No. and Name	12 COED-Y-BRENIN	Map Sheet Nos.	
Flying Height (metres)	3000	Direction Flown	N
Flight Conditions	GENERALLY CLEAR 5% CLOUD OVERALL	No. of Lines	3
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	39	No. of Scan Lines	189
Film Forward Overlap (%)	60	No. of CCTs	1
Ground Speed (knots)	170	Scan Speed rps	12.5
Time Flown (GMT)	1231-1257	Tape Footage	188
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction	YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Area No. and Name	13 PORTSMOUTH	Map Sheet Nos.	
Flying Height (metres)	1539	Direction Flown	N
Flight Conditions	CLOUD SHADOW	No. of Lines	3
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	45	No. of Scan Lines	24,000
Film Forward Overlap (%)	60	No. of CCTs	3
Ground Speed (Knots)	170	Scan Speed rps	25
Time Flown (GMT)	1607- 1623 REFLY PERIOD ONLY.	Tape Footage	498
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction	YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

NERC 1983 SURVEY

Area No. and Name	14 LOCH LEIGH	Map Sheet Nos.
Flying Height (metres)	1385	Direction Flown N
Flight Conditions	CLOUD OVERHEAD & ALONG SHORELINE	No. of Lines 4
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	29	No. of Scan Lines 74,100
Film Forward Overlap (%)	60	No. of CCTs 2
Ground Speed (knots)	170	Scan Speed rps 25
Time Flown (GMT)	1653-1747	Tape Footage 348
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Area No. and Name	16 DERBYSHIRE	Map Sheet Nos.
Flying Height (metres)	739 769	Direction Flown W E/W
Flight Conditions	CLOUD SHADOW + TURBULANCE CLEAR	No. of Lines 8 + 8
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	209	No. of Scan Lines 224,800, 106,500
Film Forward Overlap (%)	60	No. of CCTs 0 + 16
Ground Speed (Knots)	150 125/155	Scan Speed rps 50
Time Flown (GMT)	1319-1433 1128-1204	Tape Footage 3910/2686
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

FIRST FLOWN 06/09/83

SECOND FLIGHT 02/10/83

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

NERC 1983 SURVEY

Area No. and Name	18 LOCH ASSYNT	Map Sheet Nos.
Flying Height (metres)	2308	Direction Flown N/S
Flight Conditions	LOW SUN ANGLE/SHADOW. SOME CLOUD ON PEAKS	No. of Lines 9 5 LINES ONLY PRESENTED
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	262	No. of Scan Lines 132,300
Film Forward Overlap (%)	60	No. of CCTs 5
Ground Speed (knots)	170	Scan Speed rps 25
Time Flown (GMT)	1121 - 1250	Tape Footage 3010
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction YES
Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX	
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens	
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder	

Area No. and Name	19A DARTFORD	Map Sheet Nos.
Flying Height (metres)	2154	Direction Flown N/S
Flight Conditions	CLEAR	No. of Lines 4
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	36	No. of Scan Lines 45,100
Film Forward Overlap (%)	60	No. of CCTs 4
Ground Speed (Knots)	170	Scan Speed rps 25
Time Flown (GMT)	1640 - 1629	Tape Footage 645
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction YES
Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX	
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens	
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder	

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

NERC 1983 SURVEY

Area No. and Name	19B HENLEY	Map Sheet Nos.
Flying Height (metres)	2154	Direction Flown N/S
Flight Conditions	CLEAR	No. of Lines 4
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	48	No. of Scan Lines 37,900
Film Forward Overlap (%)	60	No. of CCTs 4
Ground Speed (knots)	170	Scan Speed rps 25
Time Flown (GMT)	1538 - 1604	Tape Footage 737
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Area No. and Name	19C POOLE (DORCHESTER)	Map Sheet Nos.
Flying Height (metres)	2000	Direction Flown N
Flight Conditions	CLEAR	No. of Lines 4
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	58	No. of Scan Lines 44,900
Film Forward Overlap (%)	60	No. of CCTs 4
Ground Speed (Knots)	170	Scan Speed rps 25
Time Flown (GMT)	1050 - 1120	Tape Footage 737
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

NERC 1983 SURVEY

Area No. and Name	22 NORTH YORKSHIRE	Map Sheet Nos.
Flying Height (metres)	1692 677	Direction Flown N
Flight Conditions	ABUNDANCE OF FULL CLOUD CLOUD ABORTED COVER	No. of Lines 3 + 10
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	207	No. of Scan Lines 27,300/ 366,300
Film Forward Overlap (%)	60	No. of CCTs 9
Ground Speed (knots)	170 140	Scan Speed rps 25 50
Time Flown (GMT)	1134-1153 1337-1539	Tape Footage 559 + 2321
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction YES

Aircraft NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX

Camera Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens

Scanner Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic
Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter
unit and Sabre III tape recorder

FIRST FLOWN 07/09/83 AM HIGH LEVEL SECOND FLIGHT 07/09/83 PM - LOW LEVEL

Area No. and Name	27 SNOWDON	Map Sheet Nos.
Flying Height (metres)	3500	Direction Flown N
Flight Conditions	GENERALLY CLEAR 5% CLOUD COVER OVERALL	No. of Lines 3
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	61	No. of Scan Lines 25,200
Film Forward Overlap (%)	60	No. of CCTs 3
Ground Speed (Knots)	170	Scan Speed rps 12.5
Time Flown (GMT)	1317 - 1351	Tape Footage 350
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction YES

Aircraft NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX

Camera Wild RCS Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens

Scanner Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic
Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter
unit and Sabre III tape recorder

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

NERC 1983 SURVEY

Area No. and Name	34 NOTTINGHAM	Map Sheet Nos.
Flying Height (metres)	508,1015,1523,2030,2538 3046, 4062	Direction Flown N
Flight Conditions	GENERAL CLOUD COVER	No. of Lines 7
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	46	No. of Scan Lines 192,900
Film Forward Overlap (%)	60	No. of CCTs 3
Ground Speed (knots)	105 AND 170	Scan Speed rps 50
Time Flown (GMT)	1126 - 1230	Tape Footage 696
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Area No. and Name	36 WINCHESTER/PETERSFIELD	Map Sheet Nos.
Flying Height (metres)	800 492	Direction Flown N
Flight Conditions	CLEAR : SOME CLOUD VARIABLE LIGHT CONDITIONS	No. of Lines 1 + 3
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	82	No. of Scan Lines 2100 + 63,900
Film Forward Overlap (%)	60	No. of CCTs 1 + 6
Ground Speed (Knots)	170 110	Scan Speed rps 50
Time Flown (GMT)	1024 - 1025 : 0927 - 0949	Tape Footage 109 + 1208
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

WINCHESTER CAL LINE
FLOWN 05/09/83

PETERSFIELD FLOWN
05/10/83

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

NERC 1983 SURVEY

Area No. and Name	43 CHARTTERIS	Map Sheet Nos.	
Flying Height (metres)	2030	Direction Flown	N/S
Flight Conditions	SOME CLOUD	No. of Lines	18
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	141	No. of Scan Lines	187,400
Film Forward Overlap (%)	60	No. of CCTs	18
Ground Speed (knots)	170	Scan Speed rps	25
Time Flown (GMT)	0932 - 1136	Tape Footage	3606
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction	YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Area No. and Name	46 SOLENT	Map Sheet Nos.	
Flying Height (metres)	2030	Direction Flown	E, NW, NE
Flight Conditions	BROKEN CLOUDS	No. of Lines	4
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	0	No. of Scan Lines	58,900
Film Forward Overlap (%)	N/A	No. of CCTs	6
Ground Speed (Knots)	170	Scan Speed rps	25
Time Flown (GMT)	1029 --1110	Tape Footage	1153
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction	YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

NERC 1983 SURVEY

Area No. and Name	47 STRUMPSHAW MARSH	Map Sheet Nos.
Flying Height (metres)	3000/2000/1000	Direction Flown N.S. E.W
Flight Conditions	HAZE NO CLOUD	No. of Lines 8
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	80	No. of Scan Lines 61,000
Film Forward Overlap (%)	60	No. of CCTs 3
Ground Speed (knots)	135	Scan Speed rps 12.5, 25
Time Flown (GMT)	1245 - 1337	Tape Footage 527
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Area No. and Name	RESERVE 1 THETFORD	Map Sheet Nos.
Flying Height (metres)	2000	Direction Flown E
Flight Conditions	HAZE NO CLOUDS	No. of Lines 3
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	59	No. of Scan Lines 51,700
Film Forward Overlap (%)	60	No. of CCTs 3
Ground Speed (Knots)	135	Scan Speed rps 25
Time Flown (GMT)	1153 - 1225	Tape Footage 624
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

NERC 1983 SURVEY

Area No. and Name	RESERVE 2 LOCH LEVEN	Map Sheet Nos.
Flying Height (metres)	1262	Direction Flown NW
Flight Conditions	FULL CLOUD COVER	No. of Lines 2
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	27	No. of Scan Lines 15,500
Film Forward Overlap (%)	60	No. of CCTs 1
Ground Speed (knots)	150	Scan Speed rps 25
Time Flown (GMT)	1510 - 1520	Tape Footage 173
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Area No. and Name	RESERVE 3 ANGLESEY	Map Sheet Nos.
Flying Height (metres)	800	Direction Flown NE
Flight Conditions	GENERALLY CLEAR 5% CLOUD OVERALL	No. of Lines 2 ONLY 1 PRODUCED
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	17	No. of Scan Lines 14600
Film Forward Overlap (%)	60	No. of CCTs 1
Ground Speed (Knots)	140	Scan Speed rps 50
Time Flown (GMT)	1406 - 1412	Tape Footage 128
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

NERC 1983 SURVEY

Area No. and Name	RESERVE 4 THEOBALDS PARK	Map Sheet Nos.
Flying Height (metres)	1538	Direction Flown E.W
Flight Conditions	CLEAR	No. of Lines 3
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	0	No. of Scan Lines 52600
Film Forward Overlap (%)	N/A	No. of CCTs 3
Ground Speed (knots)	170	Scan Speed rps 25
Time Flown (GMT)	1724 - 1759	Tape Footage 854
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Area No. and Name	RESERVE 5 WESTON SUPER MARE (SHAPWICK)	Map Sheet Nos.
Flying Height (metres)	2000	Direction Flown N
Flight Conditions	CLEAR	No. of Lines 3
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	54	No. of Scan Lines 37,000
Film Forward Overlap (%)	60	No. of CCTs 3
Ground Speed (Knots)	170	Scan Speed rps 25
Time Flown (GMT)	1132 - 1157	Tape Footage 561
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

NERC 1983 SURVEY

Area No. and Name	TEST AREAS SWINDON	Map Sheet Nos.
Flying Height (metres)	462 500	Direction Flown 7 VARIABLES
Flight Conditions	HAZE CLEAR	No. of Lines 8 + 1
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	0	No. of Scan Lines 203300 + 14,300
Film Forward Overlap (%)	N/A	No. of CCTs 3 + 1
Ground Speed (knots)	105	Scan Speed rps 50
Time Flown (GMT)	1038 - 1146 : 1217 - 1223	Tape Footage 911 + 118
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Area No. and Name	EAST MIDLANDS	Map Sheet Nos.
Flying Height (metres)	500, 1000, 1500, 2000	Direction Flown
Flight Conditions	CLOUD ABOVE 1500M	No. of Lines 1 LINE FLOWN 5 1 line ABORTED TI
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	0	No. of Scan Lines 77,000
Film Forward Overlap (%)	N/A	No. of CCTs 2
Ground Speed (Knots)	110 & 140	Scan Speed rps 50
Time Flown (GMT)	1645 - 1725	Tape Footage 366
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

AREA FLOWN 18TH AUGUST 1984 SORTIE 9

NEWHAVEN 10
Dieppe 4 hrs

PORTSMOUTH 10
E EY B

BO RNEMOUTH

CHRISTCHURCH

WIMBORNE

BYDE

SEAVIEW

ST HELENS

NEWPORT

BOMBIDGE

FORLAND

WIMBORNE

FIGURE 2

FIGURE 4

NEWCASTLE UPON TYNE to	Distance
Stavanger	17; 22 hrs (seasonal)
Esbjerg	18; 21 hrs (seasonal)
Bergen	19; 24 hrs (seasonal)
Gothenburg	24; 28 hrs (seasonal)
Oslo	32 hrs (seasonal)

URE 6

FIGURE 7

EDINBURGH

14

R2

19

49

60

**HUNTING GEOLOGY AND
GEOPHYSICS LIMITED**

ELSTREE WAY
BOREHAMWOOD HERTS
WD6 1SB ENGLAND
Cables: ASTEREO
BOREHAMWOOD
Tel: 01-953 6161
Telex: 23517

**information
sheet**

AG 510

1982

DAEDALUS AIRBORNE THEMATIC MAPPER

The AADS 1268 Airborne Thematic Mapper (ATM) is an eleven channel system which covers the bands used by the Landsat 4 Thematic Mapper, the Landsat 3 MSS and the SPOT System. The prototype model was flown on a major multi-client survey in the USA in 1981 and the first production AADS 1268 was delivered to NASA/Ames in March 1982, as a modification of their AADS 1260 system. It is thus the most advanced scanner currently available.

Sophisticated image processing of ATM data collected over semiarid terrain enables geologists to obtain important new information for petroleum and mineral exploration. Whereas properly processed Landsat 1, 2, and 3 data can be used to map iron oxides, ATM can be used to segregate iron oxides into primary and secondary categories, as well as to map surface exposures of clay minerals. Since both secondary iron oxides and clay minerals are associated with basic metal deposits, the ATM offers exciting new capabilities for gold, silver, uranium, copper, lead, zinc, and other metal exploration. It also offers new capabilities for mapping surface soil alterations and vegetative anomalies which are sometimes related to ancient oil and gas seeps.

Major improvements offered in the new AADS 1268 are:

1. Versatile optical design, which can accommodate a great variety of combinations of spectrometer configurations as future needs arise.
2. Precise registration of pixels from all channels.
3. Combination of spectral bands, e.g., thematic mapper bands, not previously achievable.
4. Optional 1.25 mr IFOV field stop aperture assembly.
5. Larger collecting areas for improved radiometric sensitivity.
6. Higher performance optics and coatings.
7. Improved optical/mechanical design incorporating thermally stable materials.
8. Improved laboratory calibration equipment.

HUNTING GEOLOGY AND GEOPHYSICS LIMITED

ELSTREE WAY
BOREHAMWOOD HERTS
WD6 1SB ENGLAND
Cables: ASTEREO
BOREHAMWOOD
Tel: 01-953 6161
Telex: 23517

information sheet

AG 513

1984

HUNTING'S STANDARD ATM RAW DATA TAPE FORMAT

9 track.
1600 bpi.
Binary.

Tape blocks of 9000 bytes. These are the data for all 12 channels of one scan line.

Logical records of 750 bytes. These are the data for one band for one scan line including the pre and post amble. The scan format is:-

Byte	Contents
1 - 4	Start of frame code 01010110 10100101 10100110 10101111
5	Run number/extend line count
6 - 8	Line count (BCD)
9 - 12	Thumb wheel setting (BCD)
13 - 14	Calibration Source 1 (BCD)
15 - 16	Calibration Source 2 (BCD)
17 - 21	External digital data N.B. 2 msb of byte 17 represent scan speed. 00 12.5 scans/sec 01 25 scans/sec 10 50 scans/sec
22	S bend 4 msb Channel number 4 lsb
23	Digitized BB1
24 - 739	Video data
740	Digitized BB1
741 - 750	End of frame code

10101010 10101010

Each tape file will contain the data for a complete flight line or for 4000 tape records. (48000 scan lines).

Each tape will start with an ASCII header record containing information about the data in that file.

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